

Heavy precipitation and strong winds in storm Éowyn mostly strengthened by human-driven climate change

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Press Summary

- Storms similar to Éowyn are up to 4 hPa deeper, up to 8 km/h (10%) windier over the Atlantic coasts of Ireland and France, and up to 6 mm/day (up to 15%) wetter in the present than they would have been in the past
- Storm Éowyn was driven by very rare meteorological conditions.
- We mostly ascribe the strengthened wind and higher precipitation of Storm Éowyn to human driven climate change and natural climate variability likely played a modest role.

Event Description

Storm Éowyn, an exceptionally powerful extratropical cyclone, struck Ireland, the Isle of Man, and the United Kingdom on January 24, 2025. Named by the UK Met Office on January 21, 2025, it was the fifth storm of the 2024–25 European windstorm season. While approaching Ireland and the UK, Éowyn underwent a phase of explosive intensification, with an exceptional pressure drop of [50 hPa in 24 hours](#), leading to a minimum observed value of 939 hPa. Éowyn displayed unprecedented wind speeds, with sustained wind above 80 mph (135 km/h) and gusts reaching up to 135 mph (217

km/h) in Cairnwell, Scotland, making it comparable to a [category 1 hurricane](#), leading to widespread red weather warnings across the affected regions ([Wikipedia](#)). The impact of Storm Éowyn was devastating. Over 1 million people in Ireland, Northern Ireland, and Scotland were left without electricity and sustained significant property damage, including the collapse of a 100-year-old building in Hale, Manchester, and the fall of a 166-year-old Himalayan cedar at the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh. Tragically, [the storm claimed two lives](#), both due to falling trees. In response to the widespread damage, international support crews from Finland, Austria, and France were flown in to expedite recovery efforts (see [APNews](#), [The Irish Sun](#), [The Times & The Sunday Time](#), [The Sun](#)).

27-Jan-2025 CNRS-IPSL (ERA5+GFS Data)

ClimaMeter for Storm Éowyn 24-Jan-2025

LSCE-IPSL
www.ipsl.fr

Influenced by
Natural Variability

Strengthened by
Climate Change

Rare
Meteorological Event

Very Exceptional
Meteorological Event

www.climameter.org
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Surface Pressure Anomalies Temperature Anomalies

Precipitation Data

Windspeed Data

Surface Pressure Changes Temperature Changes

Precipitation Changes

Windspeed Changes

Similar Past Events

Changes in Urban Areas

The *Surface Pressure Anomalies* reveal a large negative (cyclonic) anomaly over the UK and Central Europe. In the context of Atlantic extratropical storms, this setup can be associated with extensive precipitation and intense wind due to the deepening pressure gradient. *Temperature Anomalies* show temperatures up to 4 °C warmer than average over continental Europe, particularly in Northern France, Belgium, The Netherlands, and Northern Germany, extending up to Denmark and the UK (2 °C), affected by the warm sector of the cyclone. *Precipitation Data* show intense daily precipitation (up to 50 mm/day) over Ireland, UK, France and North Sea. *Windspeed data* show large areas of Europe and Atlantic affected by sustained winds between 40 km/h and 60 km/h, and higher than 60 km/h over the sea and the coasts of Ireland and Scotland.

Climate and Data Background for the Analysis

The [IPCC AR6 Chapter 11](#) states that climate change affects storminess in Europe, with negative repercussions that are exacerbated by rising sea levels and heavy precipitation. From a global warming level of 2 °C or higher a slightly increased frequency and amplitude of extratropical cyclones, strong winds and extratropical storms is projected for northern Europe with medium confidence ([IPCC AR6 WGI Chapter 12](#)). The extreme precipitation and pluvial flooding have shown a strong trend in Northern Europe in the past and there is a strong consensus among models from global to kilometer scale convection permitting models that are going to increase from 2 °C or higher ([IPCC AR6 WGI Chapter 12](#)).

Recent studies, such as [Ginesta et al. \(2024\)](#), confirm that the intensity of recent storms, including both wind speed and precipitation, is likely to increase in the most impacted regions of Europe.

Our analysis approach rests on looking for weather situations similar to those of the event of interest having been observed in the past. For storm Éowyn, we have

medium-high confidence in the robustness of our approach given the available climate data, as the event is similar to other past events in the data record.

ClimaMeter Analysis

We analyse here (see [Methodology](#) for more details) how events similar to Storm Éowyn have changed in the present (1987–2023) compared to what they would have looked like if they had occurred in the past (1950–1986) in the region [20°W 10°E 45°N 65°N]. *Surface pressure changes* indicate that storms resembling Éowyn exhibit pressure anomalies up to 4 hPa deeper over Northern Ireland in the present than in the past. *Temperature changes* show up to 5°C warmer anomalies with respect to the past, especially over Scandinavia. *Precipitation changes* indicate wetter conditions (+6 mm/day) over Northern Ireland and Scotland, as well as over Northern France, and Norway. *Windspeed changes* suggest that these storms are now up to 8 km/h windier over Scotland, Ireland and the English Channel. From the analysis of urban areas we found that Dublin, Galway and Cork all experience up to 4km/h windier conditions. We also note that Similar Past Events display comparable seasonal distribution between past and present periods.

Finally, we find that sources of natural climate variability, notably the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation, may have only partly influenced the event. This means that the changes we see in the event compared to the past may be mostly due to human driven climate change.

Conclusion

Based on the above, we conclude that windstorms similar to Storm Éowyn are more intense with up to 4 hPa deeper, up to 8 km/h (10%) windier over the Atlantic coasts of Ireland and France, and up to 6 mm/day (up to 15%) wetter in the present than they would have been in the past. We interpret Storm Éowyn as an event driven by rare

meteorological conditions whose characteristics can be mostly ascribed to human driven climate change.

Additional Information : Complete Output of the Analysis

- NB1: The following output is specifically intended for researchers and contain details that are fully understandable only by reading the methodology described in Faranda, D., Bourdin, S., Ginesta, M., Krouma, M., Noyelle, R., Pons, F., Yiou, P., and Messori, G.: A climate-change attribution retrospective of some impactful weather extremes of 2021, *Weather Clim. Dynam*, 3, 1311-1340, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wcd-3-1311-2022>, 2022.
- NB2: Colorscales may vary from the ClimaMeter figure presented above.

The figure shows the average of surface pressure anomaly (msl) (a), average 2-meter temperatures anomalies (t2m) (e), cumulated total precipitation (tp) (i), and average wind-speed (wspd) in the period of the event. Average of the surface pressure analogs found in the counterfactual (b) and factual

period (c), along with corresponding 2-meter temperatures (f, g), cumulated precipitation (j, k), and wind speed (n, o). Changes between present and past analogues are presented for surface pressure Δslp (d), 2 meter temperatures Δt_{2m} (h), total precipitation Δtp (i), and windspeed Δw_{spd} (p): color-filled areas indicate significant anomalies with respect to the bootstrap procedure. Violin plots for past (blue) and present (orange) periods for Quality Q analogs (q), Predictability Index D (r), Persistence Index Θ (s), and distribution of analogs in each month (t). Violin plots for past (blue) and present (orange) periods for ENSO (u), AMO (v) and PDO (w). Number of the Analogues occurring in each subperiod (blue) and linear trend (black). Values for the peak day of the extreme event are marked by a blue dot. Horizontal bars in panels (q,r,s,u,v,w) correspond to the mean (black) and median (red) of the distributions. The data are used for the analysis are ERA5 Reanalyses data completed with daily averages from the GFS forecast system.